

MODERN TEACHING METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

Furkat Jumayev Soatmumin ogli

Termez State University, foreign philology,

German language 3rd year student

Annotation: This article is based on a modern and new teaching method in a foreign language or German language class. You will also learn about the Master-Apprentice system.

Keywords: Education Law, Foreign Language, German, National Training Program, Vocabulary.

Even before the independence of our country, the first head of our state I.A.Karimov did not allow young people to enjoy the achievements of modern science and technology, in general, science, to create conditions for them to become highly qualified professionals. had emphasized that it could not be radically changed. Today, special attention is paid to education, teaching and learning foreign languages, which puts even more responsibilities on our teachers. The first President of our country IA Karimov stated that the main direction of the development of modern science requires knowledge of world languages, especially the languages of advanced technical thinking. We should take all possible measures to encourage the study of English, French, German, Spanish, Russian and other languages. The main goal and driving force of the reforms in the republic is the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for the realization of individual interests, the harmonious development and well-being of man, the transformation of outdated thinking and patterns of social behavior. An important condition for the development of Uzbekistan is the formation of a perfect system of training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal values, the achievements of modern culture, economy, science, engineering and technology. It is known that the main link in public education is the system of continuing education. Therefore, it is

necessary to pay special attention to this issue. The fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan has gained state independence and chosen a specific path of economic and social development has necessitated the reorganization of the structure and content of training and to take a number of measures: introduction of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan, introduction of new curricula, programs, textbooks, development of modern didactic support; required the attestation and accreditation of educational institutions, the establishment of new types of educational institutions. At the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Islam Karimov said: We consider it our main task to bring up healthy, independent-minded children, a new generation that can meet today's needs. Involvement of students in the "Teacher-Apprentice" system in the training of targeted personnel with experienced specialists of existing production organizations in the water management system, so that today's young people have a comprehensive knowledge in their field:

1. Students will have the opportunity to fully learn the production processes of the enterprise by being appointed as apprentices to leading specialists in their field.
2. Acquire professional secrets and basic skills as a result of motivation and referral to the profession by the teacher.
3. Students form practical work, experience and skills in the field, inseparable from study through the schedule established by the department, create the basis for them to work in manufacturing enterprises without probation after graduation, and so on.

When we learn a foreign language, we have to learn and master the teaching methods of the language we are learning. Modern foreign language classes require the study of phonetics, vocabulary and grammar of the language based on teaching methods. Because teaching based on teaching methods is effective. Teaching methods allow you to quickly and easily learn foreign words and increase your vocabulary. We know that methods are the basis of success and experience in the organization of education. Learning a foreign language is a complex process. Methods also play an important role in the organization of German language classes.

The use of a variety of methods by a foreign language teacher in the organization of the lesson is the key to the effectiveness of the lesson. We know that each lesson is planned. Any activity based on research is a productive activity. The learning process will be more effective if the teacher is active and creative in researching the topic without having to master the German language materials in a ready way. Problem-based learning provides a good opportunity for such research and creativity. This method serves as a tool for the comprehensive development of the individual and his intellectual activity. Although the concept of problem-based learning has emerged in the pedagogical literature in recent years, the idea of inquisitive teaching has a history of more than a thousand years. It was the product of knowledge and research, as noted by Eastern thinkers. Abu Ali idn Sina (980-1037) in his Encyclopaedia showed the advantage of acquiring knowledge by overcoming difficulties. Nowadays, there is a growing interest in using problem-based learning methods to increase the effectiveness of education. Problem-based learning activities allow students to search for, study, analyze, and even draw conclusions on their own. In this process, the teacher creates the conditions for the development, formation, education and upbringing of the individual and the team, acts as a leader, a guide. This leads to the idea that it is possible to try to modernize the learning process, that is, to turn teaching into a methodological process that produces clearly guaranteed results. The main reasons for the emphasis on the use of problem-based learning methods in education are:

First of all, there is a wide range of opportunities for person-centered learning in problem-based learning.

The Law on Education and the National Training Program pay special attention to the implementation of developmental education.

Second, problem-based learning methods allow for the widespread introduction of a systematic approach to the educational process.

Third, the problem-based teaching method encourages the teacher to pre-design the methodological chain so that the teacher can lead the students into the problem on the topic and control the process.

Fourth, because problem-based learning methods are based on the use of new tools and information methods, their application will greatly facilitate and ensure the implementation of the requirements of the National Training Program. Problem-based learning activities allow young people to express their views on important life achievements and problems, to think, and to justify their views. In today's innovative process, to solve the problems facing the education system, we need people who are able to absorb new information and evaluate their own knowledge, make the necessary decisions, think independently and freely. Therefore, the role and importance of problem-based learning methods, interactive methods, innovative technologies in the educational process is invaluable. When we learn a foreign language, we combine the phonetics, grammar, and vocabulary of the language being studied. I want to give a general idea about German vocabulary. German lexicon refers to the richness of the German lexicon. The more vocabulary he acquires in the process of learning German, the more he can communicate and think freely in German. To achieve this, the organization of German language lessons on the basis of problem-based teaching methods has a positive effect. Teaching a foreign language should not be limited to just one method. Creativity is also an exercise in practice, but it remains creative. The use of different teaching methods by teachers is one of the most important requirements of our time. In order to determine how a teacher can work with students in foreign language teaching, it is important to pay attention to the process of teaching the subject. The process of teaching German is closely intertwined, with the development of speaking skills and the acquisition of language material. The complex techniques and technologies that are rapidly entering our way of life are becoming more and more entrenched in the minds of our children. In such a situation, it takes a great deal of skill on the part of the teacher to teach a student new knowledge, to teach him to read and to do research. Naturally, this process encourages every educator who loves, respects and respects his profession, to teach and discover new pedagogical methods and techniques, technologies. The use of teaching methods in experimental fields allows for more effective and positive teaching methods to be used in the classroom. The use of

modern methods in the classroom refers to the activation of students, that is, to ensure that the student is active throughout the lesson. In conclusion, the goal is to organize today's educational process on the basis of teaching methods, to increase the effectiveness of education as a result of the use of problem-based teaching methods in the classroom.

References:

1. I. Karimov. "Uzbekistan on the Threshold of the 21st Century: Threats to Security, Conditions of Stability and Guarantees of Development." —Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 1997
2. Tokhtapolat Riskiev. The dream of a harmoniously developed generation. State Scientific Publishing House "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". Tashkent. 2000 y. 34-37 –B.
3. Binovich L. E., Grishin N. N. German-Russian phraseological dictionary / ed. Dr. Malige-Clappenbach and K. Agricola. 2nd edition, rev. and add. M.: Russian language, 1975.656 p.